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PROTOCOL FOR A SCOPING REVIEW

Title: Spatial Navigation Metrics in Virtual Reality-Based Instrumental
Activities of Daily Living Tasks for Mild Cognitive Impairment
Screening: A Scoping Review Protocol

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1. REVIEW TEAM

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2. BACKGROUND

Virtual Reality (VR) simulations of Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL) offer ecologically valid assessment of subtle functional decline in Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI). However, there is currently no consensus on which spatial-behavioural metrics should be extracted from these tasks, nor on the theoretical rationale guiding that choice.

This scoping review aims to systematically map the landscape of spatial navigation and behavioural metrics extracted from VR-IADL tasks used for screening or assessing MCI in older adults.

3. RESEARCH QUESTION (PCC Framework)

Population: Older adults (≥ 60 years) with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI)

Concept: Spatial navigation and behavioural metrics extracted from
VR-based IADL performance, and their theoretical rationale

Context: Immersive or non-immersive Virtual Reality simulations of
Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (e.g., supermarket, kitchen, bus, kiosk, museum)

Main Question: In VR-IADL studies for MCI screening in older adults, (a) which spatial navigation and behavioural metrics have been extracted, and (b) what is the theoretical or methodological rationale underlying the selection of those metrics?

4. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Inclusion:

- Older adults (mean age \geq 60 years) with MCI diagnosis (Petersen, Albert, DSM-5 criteria)
- VR simulation of at least one IADL task
- Reports at least one quantitative behavioural/spatial metric from VR performance
- Primary empirical research (original data)
- Published in English in a peer-reviewed journal

Exclusion:

- Review articles, editorials, protocols, conference abstracts, dissertations
- Studies focusing exclusively on dementia without MCI subgroup
- Pure spatial navigation tasks without IADL context
- Studies reporting only pre-post neuropsychological test scores without VR behavioural metrics

5. INFORMATION SOURCES AND SEARCH STRATEGY

Database: PubMed

Supplementary: Google Scholar, Scopus, PsychInfo, Embase, Web of science

Search Date: 25 May 2026

Full search strategy available in Supplementary File 1 of the final manuscript.

6. STUDY SELECTION

- Titles/abstracts screened by one reviewer
- Full texts assessed independently against eligibility criteria
- Disagreements resolved through discussion with supervisor

7. DATA EXTRACTION

Standardised extraction form including:

- Study characteristics (author, year, country, design)
- Population characteristics (sample size, age, MCI criteria)
- VR-IADL task type and technology
- Spatial/behavioural metrics reported
- Data extraction method (automatic vs. manual)
- Theoretical rationale for metric selection
- Main findings

8. SYNTHESIS

- Descriptive frequencies for categorical variables
- Metrics grouped into five overarching categories (Time, Errors, **Full Professor**Path Length, Speed, Complex/Composite Indices)
- Qualitative thematic analysis of theoretical justifications
- No formal risk-of-bias assessment (per scoping review methodology)

9. REGISTRATION

This protocol was registered prior to data extraction.

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